

Local deforestation spillovers induced by forest moratoria: Evidence from Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

Moratoria on commodities produced in deforestation-risk areas have been shown to be highly effective in reducing deforestation within targeted areas. Various studies have shown, however, that such policies are prone to large local spillover effects, i.e., non-trivial changes (reductions or increases) in the amount of deforestation in areas just outside the direct scope of the moratorium. Little is known about the direction and magnitude of local spillover effects that may have been induced by the Indonesian forest moratorium, an anti-deforestation policy enacted in 2011 that covers around a third of Indonesia's terrestrial area and that is of high importance in meeting international deforestation goals. Here, we empirically assess the evidence of spillover effects near the Indonesian moratorium boundaries, using several proximity metrics and a panel dataset spanning the years 2001–2018. Based on our negative binomial fixed effects regressions, we estimate that the moratorium induced 1324 km² of deforestation in areas located within 10 km of the targeted areas in the period 2011–2018, most of which occurred near conservation and protection forests. Evidence of spillover effects is also strong within concession areas slated for development. This suggests that companies may have shifted their planned production activities from areas targeted by the moratorium to neighbouring concession areas, resulting in additional forest loss. To minimize or halt such spillover effects, the scope of the Indonesian moratorium could be expanded to high-deforestation risk areas, such as forest areas outside mountainous regions, with relatively high GDP per capita and high agro-ecological suitability for oil palm plantations. In addition, a higher uptake of certification schemes and increased international finance would complement the moratorium, helping to reduce incentives to deforest both within and outside the moratorium areas.

1. Introduction

In recent years, efforts by governments, corporations and civil society to curb deforestation have steadily increased (Brown and Zarin, 2013; Geldmann et al., 2019; Lambin et al., 2018). Typical examples of anti-deforestation policies include protected areas (Bebber and Butt, 2017), agri-environmental certification schemes (van der Ven et al., 2018) and moratoria on commodities produced in deforestation-risk areas (Nolte et al., 2017; Sloan, 2014). The rise in these policies has been accompanied by an increase in studies employing quasi-experimental methods and counterfactual thinking to assess their effectiveness (Börner et al., 2016). The central research question

underlying these studies has been: “what would have happened in terms of deforestation in the absence of the policy intervention?”. While these studies typically control for the influence of other variables to estimate the effect of the intervention (e.g. agricultural suitability and market accessibility), they are often limited to areas falling directly within the scope of the policy, thus overlooking potential spillover effects on neighbouring or more distant areas (see e.g. Carlson et al., 2018; Panlasigui et al., 2018). Failing to account for spillover effects may give rise to misleading conclusions and policy recommendations (Ewers and Rodrigues, 2008; Pfaff and Robalino, 2017).

There is a growing body of evidence suggesting that land development restrictions, such as commodity moratoria, may trigger

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deforestation spillovers (positive or negative) to areas falling beyond the direct scope of the policy (Dou et al., 2018; Fuller et al., 2019; Magliocca et al., 2019; Meyfroidt and Lambin, 2009). As an example, Moffette and Gibbs (2019) provided empirical evidence that two highly effective anti-deforestation policies targeting the soy and cattle production sectors in the Brazilian Amazon displaced agricultural production to surrounding areas, thus causing further deforestation outside the targeted areas. Such displacement of agricultural production activities – often referred to as activity leakage (Meyfroidt et al., 2018) – is more likely to occur if there is a lack of off-farm employment alternatives and if neighbouring areas can be substituted for the restricted areas (Atmadja and Verchot, 2012). However, other studies have also found that anti-deforestation policies may also give rise to boosting effects. In this case, less deforestation is observed in neighbouring areas than would have occurred in the absence of the intervention (Giudice et al., 2019; Heilmayr et al., 2020; Herrera, 2015). This may occur if restrictions on land development slow down regional investments in roads and other types of infrastructure, thus reducing the risk of deforestation (Herrera, 2015).

One anti-deforestation policy that has not received much attention in the scientific literature is the Indonesian forest moratorium. Indonesia is one of the world's largest emitters of greenhouse gases and the forest moratorium was, at the time of its enactment, considered to be the single policy with the largest mitigation potential (Wijaya et al., 2017). Implemented in 2011 as part of a 'REDD+ Readiness' programme in collaboration with Norway, the moratorium suspended the granting of new concession licenses for logging, oil palm and wood fibre concessions within designated areas with the aim of reducing deforestation and associated CO₂ emissions (Austin et al., 2012; President of Indonesia, 2011; Sloan, 2014). Existing concession licenses were exempt. Although the moratorium was initially established for two years, it was extended three times before being made permanent in 2019 (Mongabay, 2019a). The extent of the moratorium has been subject to 15 revisions between 2011 and 2018 but varies in the range of 64 – 67 M ha or 34 – 35% of Indonesia's total terrestrial area, depending on which (revised) moratorium map is considered (Ministry of Environment and Forestry, 2021). The moratorium covers three different types of areas, namely conservation and protection forests, peatlands and primary forests, all designated by the Indonesian Ministry of Environment and Forestry (note that the designated peatlands and primary forests do not cover all Indonesian peatlands and primary forests). Conservation and protection forests include nature reserves and forests designated to safeguard certain hydrological services, both of which were already legally protected when the moratorium was enacted in 2011 (Murdiyarso et al., 2011). Although this implies that the moratorium bestowed no additional legal protection on conservation and protection forests, the moratorium may have strengthened law enforcement within these areas, thus contributing to the declining deforestation rates in recent years (World Resources Institute, 2019). The remaining moratorium areas designated as either peatlands or primary forests are much smaller and comprise only 20% of the total moratorium extent according to the 8th revised moratorium map (Ministry of Environment and Forestry, 2021). However, these areas largely constitute additional protection (meaning they were largely unprotected before 2011). Both the expansion of legally protected areas and the increase in law enforcement may have given rise to local spillover effects.

Very few studies have attempted to assess the effectiveness of the moratorium in reducing deforestation in Indonesia. Busch et al. (2015) estimated that if the moratorium had been in place from 2000 to 2010, the total deforested area would have been reduced by 1160 – 3050 km², which equates to 1.0 – 2.7% of the total estimated deforestation over that time. However, since their analysis was solely based on data on the decade preceding the moratorium, it did not provide an indication of the actual effectiveness following implementation. Conversely, both Suwarno et al. (2018) and Chen et al. (2019) explored potential post-implementation impacts of the moratorium, but did not consider

possible displacement effects beyond the moratorium boundaries. Given that similar anti-deforestation policies enforced in other countries have triggered large spillovers to areas within 10 km of the targeted areas (Bruggeman et al., 2018; Fuller et al., 2019; Robalino et al., 2017), it is conceivable that similar effects have occurred in Indonesia in the wake of the forest moratorium. Therefore, to effectively govern Indonesia's remaining forests, a better understanding of the effectiveness of the Indonesian moratorium is needed, considering the potential for local deforestation spillovers.

The objective of this paper is to empirically assess the direction and magnitude of local spillovers in the direct neighbourhood of Indonesian forest moratorium areas. We define areas located in the direct neighbourhood of a moratorium border on the basis of several proximity metrics and employ an econometric model to assess whether there is a strong statistical relationship between deforestation and proximity to a moratorium border after the enactment of the moratorium. In addition, we show how the spillover effects have varied across space and over time; and employ matching methods to explore the robustness of our results.

2. Methodology

2.1. Study area and data processing

Our analysis sought to examine how proximity to the moratorium border affected deforestation outcomes in the post-moratorium period (i.e., from 2011 onwards). To account for both spatial and temporal variation in deforestation, we exploited a panel dataset spanning the years 2001 – 2018, with the annual deforested area as our dependent variable, using data on tree cover loss from Hansen et al. (2013, 2019), aggregated to a resolution of 5 × 5 km. Deforestation was defined as any tree cover loss (in ha) within areas with at least 30% canopy cover, following the official forest definition of Indonesia (Ministry of Environment and Forestry, 2016). Tree cover gain was not considered as the Hansen et al. data do not distinguish between plantation forests and natural forests (Tropek et al., 2014). To explore the sensitivity of our results to the choice of forest definition, we report alternative results using 2 different forest definitions in Appendix C, based on canopy cover thresholds of 10% and 60%.

Proximity to the moratorium border was measured using the 8th revised moratorium map from (Ministry of Environment and Forestry of The Republic of Indonesia, 2021) Indonesia's Ministry of Environment and Forestry of the Republic of Indonesia (2021, see Fig. 1), published in May 2015 and digitized by Greenpeace (2021). As the year 2015 is near the middle of our study period, the 8th revised moratorium map provides a more representative spatial overview of the moratorium extent than more recent maps. Nevertheless, to explore the sensitivity of our results depending on the choice of moratorium map, we also considered an alternative moratorium map based on the intersection of the initial moratorium map (published in July 2011) and the 15th revised moratorium map (published in December 2018), shown in Fig. 1 of Appendix D. There are no major spatial differences between both maps as the percentage of overlap (intersection over union) amounts to 93%. Both moratorium maps consist of a patchwork of many disjoint polygons spread out across thousands of islands that are designated as either primary forest, peatland or conservation and protection forest. These different types of moratorium areas are officially mutually exclusive, even though it has been recognized that areas designated as peatland may contain primary forest and vice versa, according to different land cover maps (Murdiyarso et al., 2011).

As the risk of spillover effects is arguably higher near areas that were not already protected before the enactment of the moratorium, we distinguished between moratorium areas that constituted additional protection and areas that were already protected before the enactment of the moratorium, in our analysis. Whilst areas designated as conservation and protection forests were already protected before the

Fig. 1. Map of Indonesia showing the spatial extent of the three different types of areas covered by the moratorium, based on the 8th revised moratorium, first published in 2015 by the Indonesian Ministry of Environment and Forestry and digitized by Greenpeace (2021). The pie chart presented in the top right of the figure shows the percentage of the different types of area covered by the moratorium.

enactment of the moratorium, 89% of all areas designated as primary forest and 98% of all areas designated as peatlands were not, based on data from the Indonesian Ministry of Environment and Forestry (2010, see Fig. 2 of Appendix D). Since spillovers to neighbouring areas are less likely to occur if the area targeted by the moratorium is relatively small (Sinclair et al., 2012) or if the risk of deforestation was already low (Di Lallo et al., 2017), we excluded moratorium polygons smaller than 50 km² and grid cells with less than 1% forest cover at the start of 2011, and limited our analysis to the 5 largest Indonesian islands (see Fig. 3 of Appendix D for a map of these islands). Together, these islands capture 94% of all deforestation in the pre-moratorium period. Since a deforested grid cell does not add any meaningful variation to the sample,

observations after 2011 within fully deforested grid cells were set to missing (this only applied to one grid cell in our sample). As mountainous areas are typically at minimal risk of development and hence unlikely to be affected by spillovers (Busch and Ferretti-Gallon, 2017; Edwards et al., 2019), we also excluded grid cells with average elevation exceeding 3000 m and average slopes exceeding 30°, based on data from Jarvis et al. (2008). For all remaining grid cells outside the moratorium boundaries ($n = 27,849$ in the case of the 8th revised moratorium map), we computed the Euclidean distance (in kilometres) from the grid cell’s centroid to the nearest moratorium border, thereby distinguishing between the different types of areas covered by the moratorium.

2.2. Exploratory data analysis

To explore the general dynamics around the moratorium borders before and after the moratorium was enacted, we smoothed the relationship between deforestation and distance to the nearest moratorium border for both periods, using a Generalized Additive Model smoother (GAM). GAMs are statistical models that incorporate non-parametric regression techniques to summarize local (non-linear) statistical relationships that can often not be detected using a linear regression model (Keele, 2008). As the magnitude of deforestation spillovers is likely to vary with distance, detecting such local statistical relationships is key for exploring the general dynamics around moratorium areas. Since our dependent variable (annual deforested area in ha) is a nonnegative, overdispersed variable with many observations without any deforestation (27% of all observations outside moratorium areas), we used a negative binomial GAM instead of a Gaussian or Poisson GAM (see Appendix A for a more detailed discussion of overdispersion and the negative binomial model).

2.3. Empirical strategy

Our empirical strategy relies on the assumption that areas in the vicinity of a moratorium area are more likely to be exposed to deforestation spillovers (positive or negative) than areas that are further away. By comparing deforestation outcomes in grid cells close to a moratorium border with outcomes in more distant grid cells in both the pre- and post-moratorium period, our analysis sought to measure the

Fig. 2. Time series of annual deforestation between 2001 and 2018 within forest areas more than 10 km away from a moratorium border and within 10 km of a moratorium border. None of the time series include deforestation within the moratorium areas. Dotted lines represent quadratic trend lines. Data on deforestation are sourced from Hansen et al. (2013, 2019).

Fig. 3. Smoothed relationship between deforestation and distance from moratorium areas within 100 km in the pre- and post-moratorium period based on (a) all moratorium areas, (b) only moratorium areas designated as Conservation and Protection Forest, (c) only moratorium areas designated as Peatland Forest and (d) only moratorium areas designated as Primary Forest. Moratorium areas smaller than 50 km² were not considered. Smoothing was done with a negative binomial one dimensional penalized regression spline with smoothing parameters selected by generalized cross-validation. Deforestation levels and distance indicators are analyzed within a 5 × 5 km² grid. Negative distances indicate Euclidean distances within moratorium areas to the closest border. Shaded areas denote 95% confidence intervals.

direction and magnitude of local spillovers. Following Moffette and Gibbs (2019), we created two different metrics to identify grid cells in the vicinity of a moratorium area. The first is a dummy variable (one that only takes the value 0 or 1) indicating whether grid cell *i* is within 10 km of a moratorium border, using the same distance threshold as Fuller et al. (2019) and Robalino et al. (2017). The second is a continuous variable ranging from 0 to 1 that equals 1 if grid cell *i* is closest to the moratorium border and 0 if it is the farthest away, based on the following formula:

$$Closeness_i = \left| \frac{Dist_i}{MaxDist} - 1 \right|, \tag{1}$$

where, *Dist_i* denotes distance to the moratorium border and *MaxDist* represents the maximum distance of all grid cells. In Appendix C, we explore the sensitivity of our results to alternative proximity metrics (using different distance thresholds, including quadratic terms etc).

A challenge when estimating the direction and magnitude of local spillovers is that the spatial coverage of the moratorium is not randomly distributed across Indonesia. Even after excluding areas with high altitude and slope (see Section 2.1), areas within and around the moratorium boundaries tend to be located in more mountainous regions with less agro-ecological suitability for oil palm plantations and less access to palm oil mills, cities and ports in comparison with areas further away (see Appendix D Figs. 4–8). This suggests that areas closer to a moratorium border may be at a lower risk of development than undeveloped areas further away. However, Fig. 2 shows that before the moratorium was enacted, areas within 10 km of a moratorium border experienced a similar trend in deforestation to areas further away. A common trend in the pre-moratorium period indicates that areas further away may provide a valid comparison group for areas within 10 km of a border (Angrist and Pischke, 2008). The post-moratorium divergence in trends shown in Fig. 2 could potentially be (partly) attributed to spillover effects.

To identify spillover effects as distinct from the effects of potential confounding variables such as commodity prices (Gaveau et al., 2018), population dynamics (Darmawan et al., 2015) or major El Niño events

(Noojipady et al., 2017), we sought to control for these variables using a multivariate negative binomial regression model, estimated with the fixest software package in R version 4.0.2 (Bergé, 2020, 2018; R Core Team, 2020, see Appendix A for further details). By including fixed effects, we can control for the influence of (unobserved) spatial differences that are constant over time (e.g., topography, soil type), as well as year trends that vary across pre-defined geographical units (e.g., population dynamics or economic development within administrative units). In addition, we controlled for the presence of concession areas since these are already designated for development and hence more likely to be deforested. Data on concession types (logging, oil palm and wood fibre concessions) were sourced from Global Forest Watch (2019a, 2019b, 2019c, see Figure 9 of Appendix D). Grid cells with less than 50% of their total area (i.e., 12.5 km²) overlapping with one of the three concession types were assumed to be outside concession areas. As both the year of establishment and the actual year of development was unknown for most concession areas, we included year trends for each concession type in our model, thus controlling for the expansion of concession areas over time. We further refined the analysis by controlling for areas that became certified in a certain year by the Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO) as certification tends to reduce the risk of deforestation (Carlson et al., 2018a; Cattau et al., 2016). Spatiotemporal data on RSPO-certified concessions were sourced from Carlson et al. (2018b).

Finally, we also controlled for the remaining forest area within each grid cell at the start of each year, as well as the total remaining forest area in neighbouring forests, using a spatial weight matrix. Accounting for the remaining forest in neighbouring areas is key, as the risk of deforestation varies with the degree of forest fragmentation (Taubert et al., 2018). The spatial weights were constructed using an inverse-distance algorithm and a distance threshold of 15 km. We also considered alternative distance thresholds of 10 and 20 km, as well as alternative spatial weight algorithms (weights based on queen and rook contiguity), but this resulted in a lower overall fit, as indicated by the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC).

More formally, we estimated the following equation for our negative

binomial model:

$$Def_{i,c,r,t} = \exp(\beta (Post_mora_t * Proximity_i) + \delta \log_{[f_0]}(For_{i,t-1}) + \eta(w'_i \log(For_{i,t-1})) + \omega RSPO_{i,t} + \alpha_i + \phi_{c,t} + \gamma_{r,t}) \quad (2)$$

Here, $Def_{i,c,r,t}$ denotes the annual deforested area in ha within grid cell i , concession type c , regency r (i.e., second-level administrative units. Indonesian: *kabupaten*) and year t ; $Post_mora_t$ is a dummy variable indicating the period after which the moratorium was enforced; $Proximity_i$ represents one of the two proximity metrics described above; $\log_{[f_0]}(For_{i,t-1})$ represents the natural logarithm of the remaining forest area (ha) in grid cell i in year $t-1$; w'_i denotes a vector of row-standardized weights placed on the natural logarithm of the remaining forest area in neighbouring grid cells, represented by the vector $\log_{[f_0]}(For_{i,t-1})$; $RSPO_{i,t}$ is a variable indicating the proportion of the area of grid cell i that was RSPO-certified at time t , α_i , $\phi_{c,t}$ and $\gamma_{r,t}$ denote fixed effects and β , δ , η and ω are parameters to be estimated. To account for temporal and spatial autocorrelation, we clustered our standard errors at the province level (Indonesian: *provinsi*). Alternative results with standards errors clustered at the island or regency level are shown in Appendix C.

We used the results of Eq. (2) to gauge how much deforestation may have been induced or avoided in areas within 10 km of a moratorium border by comparing the fitted values using the baseline covariate values with a counterfactual scenario in which no moratorium was enacted. The counterfactual scenario was constructed by predicting for each grid cell within 10 km of a border how much deforestation would have occurred in the post-moratorium period after setting β (the parameter capturing the effect of the moratorium) in Eq. (2) to zero. Thereafter, we summed the difference between the two scenarios in terms of the predicted amount of deforestation, thus arriving at an estimate of how much deforestation may have been induced or avoided by the moratorium within 10 km of its borders. Given the non-linear nature of the negative binomial model, we explore the sensitivity of this result to alternative parameter values by running a Monte-Carlo simulation in Appendix D, following Heilmayr et al. (2020).

2.4. Robustness checks

We explored the robustness of our results by (a) re-estimating Eq. (1) for several subsets of the sample (2.4.1), (b) testing how the estimated magnitude of spillover effects within 10 km of a moratorium border varies by year (2.4.2) and (c) pre-processing the sample using a matching algorithm (2.4.3).

2.4.1. Subsamples

To assess how the direction and magnitude of spillovers vary across space, we estimated the model separately for each major Indonesian island, all remaining islands not included in the baseline model (Fig. 3b and c – Appendix D) and for each of the different concession areas (note that this reduces the concession-specific year trend, $\phi_{c,t}$ in Eq. (2) to a general year trend). Given the large variation in the size of moratorium areas (Fig. 3a – Appendix D), we also sought to investigate whether forests near larger moratorium areas are more likely to be affected by spillovers than those near smaller ones, using alternative area thresholds of 0, 100, 500 and 1000 km² (see Section 2.1). Finally, we tested how the magnitude of estimated spillover effects changes when focussing on areas deemed at higher risk of development, based on a number of covariates known to influence deforestation outcomes (see Table 1 for the list of covariates; also see Busch and Ferretti-Gallon, 2017 for a meta-analysis of the spatial drivers of deforestation). This means we explored the sensitivity of the results after excluding grid cells with

Table 1

List of covariates used to match observations.

Variable	Source	Original Resolution
Elevation (m)	Jarvis et al. (2008)	90 m ²
Gross Domestic Product per Capita at Purchasing Power Parity in constant 2011 international US dollars (log)	Kummu et al. (2018)	5-minute resolution (approximately 10×10km at the equator)
Market accessibility (hours)	Travel time to the nearest city with at least 50,000 inhabitants: Weiss et al. (2018)	30-arcsec resolution (approximately 1 × 1 km at the equator)
	Travel time to the nearest port (regardless of size): Weiss et al. (2018)	Idem
Oil palm suitability (0.01–100)	Suitability estimates sourced from Version 3 of the Global Agro Ecological Zones (GAEZ) (International Food Policy Research Institute/Food and Agriculture Organization, 2012). The data are based on the SRES H3A1 emission scenario for the 2020s and control for a CO2 fertilization effect.	5-minute resolution (approximately 10×10km at the equator)
Population density (log)	Stevens et al. (2015)	100 m ²
Remaining forest area in 2010 in ha (log)	Hansen et al., (2013, 2019)	30 m ²
Slope (°)	Jarvis et al. (2008)	90 m ²
Travel time to the nearest oil palm mill (hours)	Friction surface enumerating land-based travel speed for all land pixels for the year 2015 from Weiss et al. (2018)	30-arcsec resolution (approximately 1 × 1 km at the equator)
	Coordinates of Indonesian palm oil mills (Global Forest Watch, 2019d)	N.A.

covariate values below a certain threshold, using quartiles to define the cut-off values (see Table 1 of Appendix C).

2.4.2. Temporal effects

A potential concern of our estimation strategy is that areas within 10 km of a moratorium area are perhaps fundamentally different from areas further away (e.g., due to spatial variation in market accessibility) and that our fixed effects model does not eliminate the influence of all confounding variables, resulting in omitted variable bias. In that case, we may find statistically significant effects of proximity to a moratorium border on deforestation in the years before the moratorium was implemented. Assuming such statistically significant effects are not the result of sampling variation or deforestation agents anticipating the enactment of the moratorium (which is unlikely as the moratorium was not discussed within official circles until 2010, Murdiyarso et al., 2011), this would indicate that the effect of proximity is conflated with another confounding variable for which we have not controlled. Alternatively, if our model does not suffer from omitted variable bias, we would expect to find no statistically significant parameter estimates before 2011. To test whether this is the case, we re-estimated Eq. (2) after replacing the term $Post_mora_t * Proximity_i$ by 17 year-specific proximity effects (described below), using the year 2011 as our reference year. In addition to testing whether there is a relationship between proximity and deforestation in the period before the moratorium, this also gives an indication as to how the post-moratorium spillover effects have varied over time. This means we estimated the following equation:

$$Def_{i,c,r,t} = \exp \left(\sum_{\tau=1}^7 \beta_{-\tau} * Proximity_{i,t-\tau} + \sum_{\tau=1}^{10} \beta_{+\tau} * Proximity_{i,t+\tau} + \delta \log[\overline{f_0}](For_{i,t-1}) + \eta(w'_i \log[\overline{f_0}](For_{i,t-1})) + \theta RSPO_{i,t} + \alpha_i + \phi_{c,t} + \gamma_{r,t} \right), \quad (3)$$

where the first summation term $\sum_{\tau=1}^7 \beta_{-\tau}$ captures 7 lags or post-treatment effects for each year from 2012 up to and including 2018 and the second summation term $\sum_{\tau=1}^{10} \beta_{+\tau}$ captures 10 anticipatory or pre-treatment effects for each year from 2001 up to and including 2010.

2.4.3. Matching

Many studies have found that pre-processing data by matching methods can improve the performance of the fixed effects models (Ferraro and Miranda, 2017; Ho et al., 2007; Jones and Lewis, 2015). Pre-processing in this context means that regression analysis is done on a subset of the data where the treated and control groups are matched such that they have similar covariate distributions, with the aim of minimizing selection bias. To balance covariate distributions between grid cells within 10 km from a moratorium border and grid cells further away, we used genetic matching, an evolutionary search algorithm that iteratively checks and improves covariate balance (Diamond and Sekhon, 2013, see Appendix B for further details). To ensure that only observations were matched that are reasonably similar, we used a caliper width (a tolerance level indicating the maximum allowed dissimilarity between observations) of 0.2 times the standard deviation, as recommended by Austin (2011).

Matching was done with replacement on all variables listed in Table 1. For time-varying covariates (i.e., population density and GDP per capita), matching was done using the values from the year 2010. The reason we picked the year 2010 is that matching should not be done on observations that may have been affected by the moratorium (Stuart, 2010), and the moratorium was not announced until 2011. Balance was assessed by means of standardized mean differences, empirical quantile-quantile plots and Kolmogorov-Smirnov test statistics (see Figure 10 – Appendix D). After trimming the data to our matched

sample, we re-estimated Eq. (2).

3. Results

3.1. Evidence of local deforestation spillovers

Fig. 3 shows how deforestation trends varied across grid cells within 100 km of the different moratorium areas in the pre- and post-moratorium period. Deforestation levels near the border generally increased in the post-moratorium period, with the peak shifting from 30 to 25 km away from the border (Fig. 3a). A similar pattern holds if only areas near conservation and protection forests are included. However, near peatland and primary forests, there is no evidence of a shift in deforestation intensity to areas closer to the border, with deforestation levels largely remaining flat in the case of peatland forests (Fig. 3c) and increasing with distance in the case of primary forests (Fig. 3d). These opposite trends in deforestation levels near moratorium areas suggest spatially heterogeneous spillover effects near the different types of area covered by the moratorium. However, they are likely to be (partly) driven by underlying trends such as the degree of forest fragmentation, the presence of concession areas and regional socio-economic developments.

To account for such confounding trends, Table 2 reports the regression estimates based on Eq. (2) for all moratorium areas (columns (1) – (2)) and the three types of area covered by the moratorium (columns (3) – columns (8)). Separate results focussing only on areas that constituted additional legal protection as of 2011 are presented in Table 3 of Appendix C. Note that the variable Closeness in columns (2), (4), (6) and (8) of Table 2 refers to the continuous proximity metric that assumes values in the unit interval, as described by Eq. (1). Results from column (1) indicate that areas within 10 km of a moratorium border (first row)

Table 2

Negative binomial regression estimates of deforestation. Positive (negative) parameter estimates indicate a positive (negative) association between the variable and deforestation, holding other factors constant. Unit of observation is the 5 x 5 km² grid cell. Standard errors are clustered at the province level and shown in parentheses. Asterisks indicate the level of statistical significance (*p < 0.10, **p < 0.05, ***p < 0.01). The variable ‘Closeness’ represents a continuous metric of proximity that assumes values in the unit interval, as described by Eq. (1). AIC denotes Akaike Information Criterion and BIC denotes Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC).

Proximity to:	Dependent variable: Deforestation (canopy cover threshold 30%)							
	All moratorium areas		Conservation Forests		Peatland Forests		Primary Forests	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
<i>Variables:</i>								
Within 10 km of border (0/1)	0.07** (0.03)		0.07*** (0.03)		0.02 (0.07)		0.03 (0.06)	
Closeness		1.24*** (0.40)		1.61*** (0.38)		-1.04 (1.14)		-1.13** (0.54)
ln(forest (ha))	1.76*** (0.10)	1.76*** (0.10)	1.76*** (0.10)	1.76*** (0.10)	1.75*** (0.10)	1.75*** (0.10)	1.75*** (0.10)	1.75*** (0.10)
ln(neighbouring forest (ha))	-0.23 (0.23)	-0.24 (0.22)	-0.23 (0.23)	-0.26 (0.22)	-0.20 (0.23)	-0.22 (0.21)	-0.20 (0.23)	-0.16 (0.21)
RSPO-certification	-0.71 (0.60)	-0.71 (0.60)	-0.71 (0.60)	-0.69 (0.60)	-0.71 (0.60)	-0.70 (0.60)	-0.71 (0.60)	-0.72 (0.60)
Dispersion parameter	0.88	0.88	0.88	0.88	0.88	0.88	0.88	0.88
<i>Fixed effects:</i>								
Grid cell	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Concession type x year	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Regency x year	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	499,870	499,870	499,870	499,870	499,870	499,870	499,870	499,870
AIC	3314,629	3314,572	3314,621	3314,416	3314,678	3314,650	3314,678	3314,550
BIC	3690,634	3690,577	3690,626	3690,421	3690,683	3690,655	3690,683	3690,555
McFadden’s adjusted Pseudo R ²	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.15

Table 3

Negative binomial regression estimates of deforestation within different concession areas. Positive (negative) parameter estimates indicate a positive (negative) association between the variable and deforestation, holding other factors constant. Unit of observation is the 5 x 5 km² grid cell. Grid cells were assumed to be located within a certain concession area (logging, oil palm or wood fibre) if at least 50% of their total area (i.e., 12.5 km²) overlapped with one of the three concession types. As some grid cells dominated by either logging concessions or wood fibre concessions may also contain oil palm concessions, the variable 'RSPO-certification' is included in all models. Standard errors are clustered at the province level and shown in parentheses. Asterisks indicate the level of statistical significance (*p < 0.10, **p < 0.05, ***p < 0.01). The variable 'Closeness' represents a continuous metric of proximity that assumes values in the unit interval, as described by Eq. (1). AIC denotes Akaike Information Criterion and BIC denotes Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC).

Concession area:	Dependent variable: Deforestation (canopy cover threshold 30%)					
	Logging concessions		Oil palm concessions		Wood fibre concessions	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
<i>Variables:</i>						
Within 10 km of border (0/1)	0.17*** (0.05)		0.06 (0.07)		0.12** (0.05)	
Closeness		2.91*** (0.78)		2.07* (1.14)		1.38 (0.96)
ln(forest (ha))	2.30*** (0.21)	2.31*** (0.21)	1.65*** (0.05)	1.65*** (0.05)	1.47*** (0.09)	1.47*** (0.09)
ln(neighbouring forest (ha))	-2.12** (0.92)	-2.20*** (0.83)	0.87*** (0.21)	0.83*** (0.23)	-0.14 (0.26)	-0.13 (0.27)
RSPO-certification	-3.95*** (0.32)	-4.06*** (0.28)	-0.87 (0.57)	-0.87 (0.57)	-1.10 (0.83)	-1.10 (0.85)
Dispersion parameter	0.56	0.56	0.87	0.87	0.75	0.75
<i>Fixed effects:</i>						
Grid cell	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Regency x year	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	110,691	110,691	59,956	59,956	56,196	56,196
AIC	543,246	543,209	534,965	534,928	469,470	469,477
BIC	618,307	618,270	582,789	582,752	514,493	514,500
McFadden's adjusted Pseudo R ²	0.16	0.16	0.08	0.08	0.10	0.10

are typically associated with more deforestation in the post-moratorium period ($p < 0.05$), holding other factors constant. More specifically, we estimate that in the period 2011 – 2018, the Indonesian moratorium induced 1324 km² of forest loss in areas within 10 km of a moratorium border, which equates to approximately 2 ha per 5 x 5 km grid cell (Figure 11 of Appendix D explores the uncertainty around this estimate using a Monte Carlo simulation). In addition, column (2) suggests that grid cells that were the closest to the moratorium border – as described by Eq. (1) – experienced 246% more deforestation ($\approx 100 \times \exp(1.24) - 100$) in the post-moratorium period than the most distant areas ($p < 0.01$). Focussing only on conservation forests (column (3) – column (4)), similar results are obtained, even though these areas were already legally protected before the enactment of the moratorium. However, consistent with Fig. 2, there is no evidence of leakage effects near peatland forests (column (5) – column (6)) as none of the parameters are statistically significant at conventional levels (i.e., $p < 0.1$). Column (8) implies that areas near primary forests may even have experienced boosting effects, as they are associated with less deforestation in the post-moratorium period than areas further away ($p < 0.05$). These results remain robust when focussing only on peatland and primary with additional legal protection (see Table 3 of Appendix C) or when using an alternative moratorium map, based on the intersection of the initial moratorium map, published in 2011, and the 15th revision of the map, published in 2018 (see Table 4 of Appendix C). To further explore the sensitivity of our results, we also considered different forest definitions (canopy cover thresholds of 10% and 60%), different distance metrics (based on different distance thresholds and a quadratic term for closeness) and different levels at which to cluster our standard errors; these did not alter any of the qualitative conclusions either (see Tables 5–7 of Appendix C and Figure 12 of Appendix 10).

3.2. Subsamples

Table 3 reports the regression estimates for the three different concession types (oil palm, logging and wood fibre). Columns (1) and (5)

reveal that there is strong evidence that the moratorium induced forest loss between 2011 and 2018 within logging and wood fibre concession areas located within 10 km of a moratorium border ($p < 0.05$), amounting to an estimated 480 and 578 km², respectively. This suggests that around 80% of all induced forest loss near moratorium areas (see Section 3.1) occurred within these areas. Re-estimating the model for different islands, we find a strong variation in the direction and magnitude of spillover effects across islands. Whilst most of the parameter estimates are positive, there is strong evidence of negative spillover effects (boosting effects) near peatlands in West Papua and near primary forests in Sumatra (see Figure 13 of Appendix D). Differences in parameter estimates across concession types and islands can potentially be explained by spatial differences in economic development (proxied by GDP per capita), agro-ecological suitability for palm oil plantations and topography, as shown by Figure 14 of Appendix D. In general, spillover effects increase in magnitude with higher GDP per capita, higher oil palm agro-ecological suitability, lower elevation and less variation in slope.

Another potential reason that could partially explain these differences in parameter estimates is that the direction and magnitude of spillover effects depend on the size of the nearest moratorium area. Figure 15 of Appendix D indicates that forests within 10 km of peatlands exceeding 500 km² or primary forests exceeding 1000 km² are associated with strong positive (more deforestation) spillover effects, whilst the evidence of spillover effects diminishes if smaller moratorium areas (< 500 km²) are included. However, there is an opposite pattern near conservation and protection forests as the evidence of leakage effects disappears if only the largest moratorium areas are included. This suggests that there is no consistent relationship between the size of an area and deforestation across different types of areas covered by the moratorium.

3.3. Temporal effects

To assess the way in which the direction and magnitude of spillover

Fig. 4. Temporal point estimates of the effect of being within 10 km of a moratorium border. The year 2011 is selected as a reference year. Error bars denote 95% confidence intervals. A point estimate is significantly different from 0 at the 0.05 level if the 95% confidence interval does not contain 0.

effects varied over time, Fig. 4a plots the temporal parameter estimates (or point estimates) of being within 10 km of a moratorium border for each individual year in both the pre- and post-moratorium period, including their 95% confidence intervals (note, the year 2011 is selected as a reference year). There are no statistically significant effects in the pre-treatment period, suggesting our model sufficiently eliminates the influence of confounding trends, at least in the pre-moratorium period. From 2014 onwards, all parameter estimates become statistically significant and increase in magnitude, indicating that spillover effects did not become prominent until 2014. Focussing only on areas near conservation forests, a similar pattern emerges. However, consistent with Table 2, there is no evidence of spillover effects near peatland and primary forests, with virtually no statistically significant effects in both the pre- and post-moratorium period.

3.4. Matching

The findings from Section 3.1 remain robust after trimming the dataset to observations within a caliper width of 0.2 times the standard deviation, which discards around 26% of the original observations (see Table 8 of Appendix C). This lends further support to the conclusion that leakage effects were particularly strong near conservation and protection forests, even though these forests were already protected before the

enactment of the moratorium. In addition, the results provide further evidence that areas near primary forests may have experienced boosting effects.

4. Discussion and conclusion

This is the first assessment of the direction and magnitude of local spillover effects that may have been induced by the Indonesian moratorium on new concession licenses. We have found strong evidence that the moratorium induced forest loss in areas within 10 km of the targeted areas, amounting to a total of 1324 km² between 2011 and 2018. This equates to 166 km² per year or 60–157% of the annual deforestation that may have been avoided by the moratorium (Busch et al., 2015). These findings suggest that the effectiveness of the moratorium may have been substantially undermined due to activity leakage. Surprisingly, the evidence of leakage is particularly strong around conservation and protection forests, even though these areas were already legally protected before the moratorium was enforced in 2011. This could be a sign that law enforcement increased within these areas following the enactment of the moratorium, thus displacing some forest-risk activities to neighbouring areas. Although local government agencies may have had limited awareness of the moratorium in the first years after implementation (Austin et al., 2014), this may have changed in recent years,

given the strong evidence of spillover effects near conservation and protection forests from 2014 onwards. However, there is also evidence that the moratorium gave rise to boosting effects – i.e., less deforestation – near primary forests. A potential explanation for this is that the moratorium discouraged investments in infrastructure near these areas, thus inhibiting further land development.

In addition, the evidence suggests that leakage effects are predominantly occurring in logging or wood fibre concession areas. This could be a sign that companies or smallholders involved in the logging or wood fibre industry originally aiming to expand their activities within moratorium areas shifted their planned activities to concession areas just outside the moratorium boundaries, causing activity leakage. Companies or smallholders involved in the oil palm industry may have been more constrained to shift their activities to neighbouring areas as these areas have relatively low agro-ecological suitability. Indeed, our sensitivity analysis confirms that the evidence of activity leakage within 10 km of moratorium areas becomes much stronger after excluding areas with low agro-ecological suitability.

We have also shown that evidence of spillover effects generally increases in smoother terrains and in areas with higher GDP per capita, potentially because it increases demand for agricultural and tropical products and access to markets (Angelsen and Kaimowitz, 1999; Cuarisma and Heger, 2019). By contrast, there is an ambiguous relationship between the size of a moratorium area and its estimated spillover effects. This is consistent with Fuller et al. (2019), who found that socioeconomic factors are more important in predicting whether a national protected area shows signs of spillover effects, than the size of a protected area.

However, our results should be interpreted with caution. Instead of displacing agricultural activities, the moratorium may have incentivized companies to intensify production within concession areas. Since the remotely-sensed dataset on tree cover loss from Hansen et al. does not distinguish between natural forests and plantation forests (Tropek et al., 2014), it is possible that the estimated spillover effects within logging and wood fibre concessions are a reflection of increased logging intensities within previously developed plantation forests instead of encroachment into natural forests designated for, but not yet developed as plantation forests. This may also be the reason why the estimated spillover effects are substantially larger within logging and wood fibre concessions than in oil palm concessions.

Moreover, our results may be biased if proximity to the moratorium border is correlated with other unobserved time-varying covariates that influence deforestation outcomes and that are unrelated to the enactment of the Indonesian moratorium. Although we have controlled for all unobserved year trends at the regency level, it is conceivable that our results are partly driven by unobserved time-varying heterogeneity within regencies. Examples of potential confounding variables within regencies include the number of political districts (i.e. the number of third-level administrative levels, Indonesian: *kecamatan*), election cycles within districts and inter-governmental fiscal transfers (Burgess et al., 2012; Pailler, 2018; Tacconi and Muttaqin, 2019). Inaccuracies in the selected moratorium map (due to the high number of revisions between 2011 and 2018) may also have influenced our results.

Finally, our study does not consider spillover effects that manifest themselves further away from the moratorium boundaries, for example due to market feedback effects. Although increases in land rents due to the moratorium are more likely to occur in the vicinity of the official moratorium border (Miranda et al., 2019), changes in commodity prices induced by the Indonesian moratorium could have driven cropland expansion much further away. Assessing such market-mediated effects is challenging as it requires information on the price-responsiveness and price-elasticities of affected commodities. Recent advances in Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) models, such as the GTAP-BIO model (Taheripour et al., 2017), provide a well-developed framework to gauge their magnitude, but often lack the fine spatial detail needed to detect local spillovers. Linking global or continental macro-economic models

with local, spatially explicit land use change models offers a promising way forward for holistic assessment of spillover effects from commodity moratoria (Johnson et al., 2020; Verburg et al., 2008). In addition, accounting for the role of local political economy factors in spatially explicit land use models is key, as land use change models solely based on commodity demand and land properties typically fail to capture deforestation dynamics (Nolte et al., 2017).

Despite these limitations, our study highlights the importance of accounting for spatially heterogeneous spillover effects when assessing land zoning policies, thereby building on previous work that has attempted to quantify such effects (Bruggeman et al., 2018; Moffette and Gibbs, 2019; Robalino et al., 2017). Further work to assess the environmental consequences of such spillover effects is recommended. To minimize or halt deforestation due to leakage, the scope of the Indonesian moratorium could be expanded to high-deforestation risk areas, such as secondary forest areas outside mountainous regions with relatively high GDP per capita and high agro-ecological suitability for oil palm plantations, consistent with the recommendations of Sloan et al. (2012) and Lim et al. (2019). The recent ban on all new licenses for oil palm plantations imposed by the Indonesian government for a period of three years could be a step forwards (Mongabay, 2019b), especially when complemented with a similar ban on all licences for logging and wood fibre concessions. In addition, a larger uptake of commodity certification schemes such as RSPO-certified palm oil or Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) certified timber could reduce the risk that the protection of forest areas within moratorium areas comes at the expense of High Conservation Value Forests (HCVFs) and High Carbon Stock Forests (HCSFs) within certified areas. Finally, scaling up international climate finance for nationwide anti-deforestation programmes such as the Indonesian moratorium could increase law enforcement and reduce incentives to deforest (Yusuf et al., 2018), as exemplified by the recent Norway-Guyana REDD+ programme (Roopsind et al., 2019).

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Floris Leijten: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft. **Sarah Sim:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Henry King:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Peter Verburg:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.landusepol.2021.105690](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2021.105690).

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